

Ricci Solitons on α -Para Kenmotsu Manifolds with Semi Symmetric Metric Connection

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published online: 24 August 2023</p> <p>Corresponding Name N.V.C. Shukla</p>	<p>In this paper we introduce notion of Ricci solitons in α-para Kenmotsu manifold with semi - symmetric metric connection. We have found the relations between curvature tensor, Ricci tensors and scalar curvature of α-para Kenmotsu manifold with semi-symmetric metric connection. We have proved that 3-dimensional α-para Kenmotsu manifold with semi -symmetric metric connection is an η-Einstein manifold and the Ricci soliton defined on this manifold is named expanding and steady with respect to the value of λ constant. It is proved that Conharmonically flat α-para Kenmotsu manifold with semi-symmetric metric connection is η-Einstein manifold.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Curvature tensor, Ricci solitons, semi-symmetric metric connection.</p> <p>Mathematics Subject Classification: .53C15,53C25,53C40,53C50</p>	

1 INTRODUCTION

In 1972 Kenmotsu [18] studied a class of contact Riemannian manifolds satisfying some special conditions and this manifolds is known as Kenmotsu manifold. Sharma and Sinha [15] started to study of the Ricci solitons in contact geometry in 1983. Later Mukut Mani Tripathi, Cornelia Livia Bejan and Mircea Crasmareanu [3], [17] and others extensively studied Ricci solitons in contact metric manifolds. In 1985, almost paracontact geometry was introduced by Kaneyuki and Williams [7] and then it was continued by many authors. Nagaraja and Premalatha [11] studied exclusively about Ricci solitons on Kenmotsu manifold in 2012. Agashe and Chafle, Liang, Pravonovic and Sengupta, Yildiz and Cetinkaya [1], [9], [12], [14] and [19] studied semi-symmetric non-metric connection in different ways

A systematic study of almost paracontact metric manifolds was carried out by Zamkovoy [21]. However such structures were also studied by Buchner and Rosca. Rosca and Venhecke [13]. Further almost Para-Hermitian Structure on the tangent of an almost Para-Co hermitian manifolds was studied by Bejan [3]. A class of α -para kenmotsu manifolds was studied by Srivastava and Srivastava [16]. We can observe that the concircular curvature tensor on Pseudo-Riemannian manifold to be of constant curvature. Hayden [9] introduced Semi-symmetric linear connection on a Riemannian manifold. Let M be an n -dimensional Riemannian manifold of class C -endowed with the Riemannian metric g and ∇ be the

Levi-Civita Connection on M^n . A linear connection $\bar{\nabla}$ defined on M^n is said to be semi symmetric [8] if its torsion tensor T is of the form

$$T(X, Y) = \eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y$$

where ξ is a vector field and η is a 1-form defined by

$$g(X, \xi) = \eta(X)$$

for all vector field $X \in \chi(M^n)$ where, $\chi(M^n)$ is the set of all differentiable vector fields on M^n . A relation between the semi-symmetric metric connection $\bar{\nabla}$ and the Levi-Civita connection ∇ on M^n has been obtained by Yano [20] which is given as

$$\bar{\nabla}_X Y = \nabla_X Y + \eta(Y)X - g(X, Y)\xi \tag{1.1}$$

2 Preliminaries

A differentiable manifold M^n of dimension n is said to have an almost paracontact (ϕ, ξ, η) -structure if it admits an $(1,1)$ tensor field ϕ , a unique vector field ξ , 1-form η such that :

$$\phi^2 = I - \eta \otimes \xi,$$

$$\phi \xi = 0,$$

$$\eta \circ \phi = 0 \tag{2.1}$$

$$\eta(\xi) = 1 \tag{2.2}$$

for any vector field X, Y on M^n . The manifold M^n equipped with an almost paracontact structure (ϕ, ξ, η) is called almost

paracontact manifold . In addition,if an almost paracontact manifold admits a pseudo-Riemannian metric satisfying

$$g(X, \xi) = \eta(X) \tag{2.3}$$

$$g(\phi X, \phi Y) = -g(X, Y) + \eta(X)\eta(Y) \tag{2.4}$$

$$g(\phi X, Y) = -g(X, \phi Y) \tag{2.5}$$

for any vector field X,Y on M^n ,where ϕ is a (1,1) tensor field, ξ is a vector field, η is a 1-form and g is the Riemannian metric.Then M is called an almost contact manifold.For an almost contact manifold M ,it follows that [9]

$$(\nabla_X \phi)Y = \nabla_X \phi Y - \phi(\nabla_X Y) \tag{2.6}$$

$$(\nabla_X \eta)Y = \nabla_X \eta(Y) - \eta(\nabla_X Y) \tag{2.7}$$

Let R be Riemann curvature tensor, S Ricci curvature tensor, Q Ricci operator we have

$$S(X, Y) = \sum_{i=1}^n g(R(e_i, X)Y, e_i) \tag{2.8}$$

$$QX = -\sum_{i=1}^n R(e_i, X)e_i \tag{2.9}$$

and

$$S(X, Y) = g(QX, Y) \tag{2.10}$$

for any vector field X,Y on M^n ,then (ϕ, ξ, η, g) ,is called an almost paracontact metric structure and the manifold M equipped with an almost paracontact metric structure is called an almost paracontact metric manifold.Further in addition,if the structure (ϕ, ξ, η, g) satisfies

$$d\eta(X, Y) = g(X, \phi Y) \tag{2.11}$$

for any vector fields X,Y on M^n .Then the manifold is called paracontact metric manifold and the corresponding structure (ϕ, ξ, η, g) , is called a paracontact structure with the associated metric g [10]. On an almost paracontact metric manifold,the (1,2) tensor field N_ϕ defined as

$$N_\phi = [\phi, \phi] - 2d\eta \otimes \xi \tag{2.12}$$

Where $[\phi, \phi]$ is the nijenhuis tensor of ϕ .If N vanishes identically,then we say that the manifold M^n is a normal almost parametric metric manifold. The normality condition implies that the almost paracomplex structure J defined on $M^n \times \mathbb{R}$

$$J(X, \lambda \frac{d}{dt}) = (\phi X + \lambda(\xi), \eta(X) \frac{d}{dt}),$$

is integrable . Here X is tangent to M^n , t is the coordinate of \mathbb{R} and λ is a differentiable function on $M^n \times \mathbb{R}$.

For an almost paracontact metric 3-dimensional manifold M^3 , the following three conditions are mutually equivalent :

(i) there exist smooth functions α, β on M^3 such that

$$(\nabla_X \phi)Y = \alpha(g(\phi X, Y)\xi - \eta(Y)\phi X) + \beta(g(X, Y)\xi - \eta(Y)X) \tag{2.13}$$

(ii) M^3 is normal,

(iii) there exist smooth functions α, β on M^3 such that

$$\nabla_X \xi = \alpha(X - \eta(X)\xi) + \beta\phi X \tag{2.14}$$

where ∇ is Levi-Civita connection of pseudo-Riemannian metric g .

A normal almost paracontact metric 3-dimensional manifold is called

(a) Para-Cosymplectic manifold if $\alpha = \beta = 0$,

(b) quasi-para Sasakian manifold if and only if $\alpha = 0$ and $\beta \neq 0$,

(c) β -para Sasakian manifold if and only if $\alpha = 0$ and β is a non- zero constant,in particular para-Sasakian manifold if $\beta = -1$

(d) α -para Kenmotsu manifold if α is a non-zero constant and $\beta = 0$ in particular para-Kenmotsu manifold if $\alpha = 1$.

3 On 3-dimensional α -para Kenmotsu manifold with semi-symmetric metric connection

In 3-dimensional α -para Kenmotsu manifold, the Ricci tensor S of Levi-Civita connection ∇ is given by

$$S(X, Y) = g(R(e_1, X)Y, e_1) - g(R(\phi e_1, X)Y, \phi e_1) + g(R(\xi, X)Y, \xi).$$

Let $M^3 (\phi, \xi, \eta, g)$ be an α -para Kenmotsu manifold [13],then we have

$$R(X, Y)Z = (\frac{r}{2} + 2\alpha^2)[g(Y, Z)X - g(X, Z)Y] - (\frac{r}{2} + 3\alpha^2)[\eta(X)g(Y, Z) - \eta(Y)g(X, Z)]\xi + (\frac{r}{2} + 3\alpha^2)[\eta(X)Y - \eta(Y)X]\eta(Z) \tag{3.1}$$

Replace $Z = \xi$ in equation (3.1), we get

$$R(X, Y)\xi = \alpha^2\eta(X)Y - \eta(Y)X, \tag{3.2}$$

$$S(X, Y) = (\frac{r}{2} + 2\alpha^2)g(X, Y) - (\frac{r}{2} + 3\alpha^2)\eta(X)\eta(Y) \tag{3.3}$$

$$S(X, \xi) = -2\alpha^2\eta(X) \tag{3.4}$$

$$(\nabla_X \phi)Y = \alpha(g(\phi X, Y)\xi - \eta(Y)\phi X) \tag{3.5}$$

$$\nabla_X \xi = \alpha(X - \eta(X)\xi) \tag{3.6}$$

Let $\bar{\nabla}$ be a linear connection and ∇ be a Riemann connection of an α -para Kenmotsu manifold M . This $\bar{\nabla}$

linear connection defined by

$$\bar{\nabla}_X Y = \nabla_X Y + \eta(Y)X - g(X, Y)\xi. \tag{3.7}$$

For α -para Kenmotsu manifold with semi-symmetric metric connection ,using (2.6),(3.5) and (3.7) we have

$$(\bar{\nabla}_X \phi)Y = \alpha[g(\phi X, Y)\xi - \eta(Y)\phi X] + \eta(Y)\phi X \tag{3.8}$$

from equation (3.7),we have

$$\bar{\nabla}_X \xi = (1 + \alpha)(X - \eta(X)\xi) \tag{3.9}$$

Let M^3 be a 3-dimensional α -para Kenmotsu manifold .The curvature tensor \bar{R} of M^3 with respect to the semi-symmetric metric connection $\bar{\nabla}$ is defined by

$$\bar{R}(X, Y)Z = \bar{\nabla}_X \bar{\nabla}_Y Z - \bar{\nabla}_Y \bar{\nabla}_X Z - \bar{\nabla}_{[X, Y]} Z, \tag{3.10}$$

with the help of (3.7) and (3.9), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\nabla}_X \bar{\nabla}_Y Z = & \nabla_X \nabla_Y Z + X\eta(Z)Y + \eta(Z) \nabla_X Y - Xg(Y, Z)\xi \\ & - \alpha g(Y, Z)X + \alpha g(Y, Z)\eta(X)\xi \\ & + \eta(\nabla_Y Z)\eta(Z)\eta(Y)X - g(Y, Z)X \\ & - g(X, \nabla_Y Z)\xi - \eta(Z)g(X, Y)\xi + g(Y, Z)\eta(X)\xi \end{aligned} \tag{3.11}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\nabla}_Y \bar{\nabla}_X Z = & \nabla_Y \nabla_X Z + Y\eta(Z)X + \eta(Z) \nabla_Y X - Yg(X, Z)\xi \\ & - \alpha g(X, Z)Y + \alpha g(X, Z)\eta(Y)\xi \\ & + \eta(\nabla_X Z)\eta(Z)\eta(X)Y - g(X, Z)Y \\ & - g(Y, \nabla_X Z)\xi - \eta(Z)g(Y, X)\xi + g(X, Z)\eta(Y)\xi \end{aligned} \tag{3.12}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} - \bar{\nabla}_{[X, Y]} Z = & - \nabla_{[X, Y]} Z - \eta(Z) \nabla_X Y + \eta(Z) \nabla_Y X \\ & - g(\nabla_X Y, Z)\xi + g(\nabla_Y X, Z)\xi. \end{aligned} \tag{3.13}$$

By using equations (3.7),(2.2),(2.3),(3.6),(3.9)(3.10),(3.11), (3.12) and(3.13) ,we get

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{R}(X, Y)Z = & R(X, Y)Z - (1 + 2\alpha)[g(Y, Z)X - \\ & g(X, Z)Y] + (1 + \alpha)[\eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y]\eta(Z) + (1 + \\ & \alpha)[\eta(X)g(Y, Z) - \eta(Y)g(X, Z)]\xi \end{aligned} \tag{3.14}$$

Replace $Z = \xi$ in equation (3.14),using (2.3) and (3.2),we have

$$\bar{R}(X, Y)\xi = \alpha(1 + \alpha)(\eta(X)Y - \eta(Y)X). \tag{3.15}$$

Replace $Y = \xi$ in equation (3.15) and using equation (2.3),we get

$$\bar{R}(X, \xi)\xi = \alpha(1 + \alpha)(\eta(X)\xi - X). \tag{3.16}$$

In (3.15) taking the inner product with Z,we have $g(\bar{R}(X, Y)\xi, Z) = \alpha(1 + \alpha)(\eta(X)g(Y, Z) - \eta(Y)g(X, Z))$. (3.17)

Thus we have

Lemma 3.1 Let M be a 3-dimensional α -para Kenmotsu manifold with the semi-symmetric metric connection, \bar{S} Ricci curvature tensor and \bar{Q} Ricci operator .Then

$$\bar{S}(X, \xi) = -2\alpha(1 + \alpha)\eta(X) \tag{3.18}$$

and

$$\bar{Q}\xi = -2\alpha(1 + \alpha)\xi \tag{3.19}$$

Proof. Contracting with Y and Z in (3.17) and summing over $i=1,2,\dots,n$,from (2.8) expression

$$\sum g(\bar{R}(e_i, Y)\xi, e_i) = \alpha(1 + \alpha)[\sum \eta(e_i)g(Y, e_i) - \eta(Y) \sum g(e_i, e_i)]$$

the proof of (3.18) is completed.Then also usnig (2.10) and (2.1),(2.2),(2.3) ,the proof of (3.19) is completed.

Lemma 3.2 Let M be a 3-dimensional α -para Kenmotsu manifold with the semi-symmetric metric connection, r scalar curvature tensor, $\bar{S}(X, Y)$ Ricci curvature tensor and $\bar{Q}X$ Ricci operator.Then it follows that

$$\bar{S}(X, Y) = (-1 + \frac{r}{2} - 3\alpha + \alpha^2)g(X, Y) + (1 - \frac{r}{2} + \alpha - 3\alpha^2)\eta(X)\eta(Y) \tag{3.20}$$

And

$$\bar{Q}X = (-1 + \frac{r}{2} - 3\alpha + \alpha^2)X + (1 - \frac{r}{2} + \alpha - 3\alpha^2)\eta(X)\xi \tag{3.21}$$

Proof. Taking inner product of equation (3.14) with U and using equation (2.3) we have

$$\begin{aligned} g(\bar{R}(X, Y)Z, U) = & g(R(X, Y)Z, U) - (1 \\ & + 2\alpha)[g(Y, Z)g(X, U) - g(X, Z)g(Y, U)] \\ & + (1 + \alpha)[\eta(Y)g(X, U) - \eta(X)g(Y, U)]\eta(Z) \\ & + (1 + \alpha)[\eta(X)g(Y, Z) - \eta(Y)g(X, Z)]\eta(U) \end{aligned} \tag{3.22}$$

Let $\{e_1, \phi e_1, \xi\}$ be a local orthonormal ϕ -basis of vector fields on α -para Kenmotsu manifold M^3 .Then, we get

$$\bar{S}(X, Y) = (-1 + \frac{r}{2} - 3\alpha + \alpha^2)g(X, Y) + (1 - \frac{r}{2} + \alpha - 3\alpha^2)\eta(X)\eta(Y) \tag{3.23}$$

from equation (3.23) ,we have

$$\bar{r} = -2 + r - 8\alpha \tag{3.24}$$

where \bar{r} is the scalar curvature with semi-symmetric metric connection.

using (3.23) and (2.10),it's verified that

$$g(\bar{Q}X, Y) = g((-1 + \frac{r}{2} - 3\alpha + \alpha^2)X + (1 - \frac{r}{2} + \alpha - 3\alpha^2)\eta(X)\xi, Y) \tag{3.25}$$

from equation (3.25),we get

$$\bar{Q}X = (-1 + \frac{r}{2} - 3\alpha + \alpha^2)X + (1 - \frac{r}{2} + \alpha - 3\alpha^2)\eta(X)\xi \tag{3.26}$$

the proof of (3.21) is completed.

4 Ricci solitons in α -para kenmotsu Manifold with semi-symmetric metric connection

Let M be a 3-dimensional α -para Kenmotsu manifold with the semi-symmetric metric connection and V be pointwise collinear with ξ (i.e. $V = b\xi$, where b is a function).Then

$$(L_V g + 2S + 2\lambda g)(X, Y) = 0$$

implies

$$0 = bg(\bar{\nabla}_X \xi, Y) + (Xb)\eta(Y) + bg(X, \bar{\nabla}_Y \xi) + (Yb)\eta(X) + 2\bar{S}(X, Y) + 2\lambda g(X, Y) \quad (4.1)$$

using (3.9) in (4.1), we get

$$0 = 2b(1 + \alpha)g(X, Y) - 2b(1 + \alpha)\eta(X)\eta(Y) + (Xb)\eta(Y) + (Yb)\eta(X) + 2\bar{S}(X, Y) + 2\lambda g(X, Y) \quad (4.2)$$

With the substitution of Y with ξ in (4.2), it follows that

$$(Xb) + (\xi b)\eta(X) + 2\lambda\eta(X) - 4\alpha(1 + \alpha)\eta(X) = 0 \quad (4.3)$$

Again replacing X by ξ in (4.3) shows that

$$\xi b = -\lambda + 2\alpha(\alpha + 1) \quad (4.4)$$

Putting (4.4) in (4.3), we obtain

$$b = (2\alpha(1 + \alpha) - \lambda)\eta \quad (4.5)$$

By applying d in (4.5), we get

$$0 = (2\alpha(1 + \alpha) - \lambda)d\eta \quad (4.6)$$

Since $d\eta \neq 0$ from (4.6), we have

$$2\alpha(1 + \alpha) - \lambda = 0 \quad (4.7)$$

By using (4.5) and (4.7), we obtain that b is constant. Hence from (4.2) it is verified

$$\bar{S}(X, Y) = -b((1 + \alpha) + \lambda)g(X, Y) + b(1 + \alpha)\eta(X)\eta(Y) \quad (4.8)$$

which implies that M is an η -Einstein manifold. This leads to the following

Theorem 4.1 If in a 3-dimensional α -para Kenmotsu manifold with the semi symmetric metric connection, the metric g is a Ricci soliton and V is a pointwise collinear with ξ , then V is a constant multiple of ξ and g is an η -Einstein manifold of the form (4.8) and Ricci soliton is steady and expanding according as $\lambda = 2\alpha(1 + \alpha)$ is zero and positive, respectively.

5 Conharmonically flat α -para Kenmotsu manifolds with the semi-symmetric metric connection

We have studied conharmonically flat α -para Kenmotsu manifolds with respect to the semi-symmetric metric connection. In a α -para Kenmotsu manifold the conharmonic curvature tensor with respect to the semi-symmetric metric connection is given by

$$\bar{K}(X, Y)Z = \bar{R}(X, Y)Z - [\bar{S}(Y, Z)X - \bar{S}(X, Z)Y + g(Y, Z)\bar{Q}X - g(X, Z)\bar{Q}Y]. \quad (5.1)$$

If $\bar{K}=0$, then the manifold M is called conharmonically flat manifold with respect to the semi-symmetric metric connection. Let M be a conharmonically flat manifold with respect to the semi-symmetric metric connection. from

(5.1), we have

$$\bar{R}(X, Y)Z = \bar{S}(Y, Z)X - \bar{S}(X, Z)Y + g(Y, Z)\bar{Q}X - g(X, Z)\bar{Q}Y \quad (5.2)$$

using (3.14),(3.20)and (3.21) in (5.1), we get

$$R(X, Y)Z - (1 + 2\alpha)[g(Y, Z)X - g(X, Z)Y] + (1 + \alpha)[\eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y]\eta(Z) + (1 + \alpha)[\eta(X)g(Y, Z) - \eta(Y)g(X, Z)]\xi = S(Y, Z)X - S(X, Z)Y + (\frac{r}{2} - 6\alpha - 2)[g(Y, Z)X - g(X, Z)Y] + (1 + \alpha)[\eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y]\eta(Z) + (1 - \frac{r}{2} + \alpha - 3\alpha^2)[g(Y, Z)\eta(X) - g(X, Z)\eta(Y)]\xi \quad (5.3)$$

Now putting $X=\xi$ in (5.3), we obtain

$$R(\xi, Y)Z = S(Y, Z)\xi - S(\xi, Z)Y + (\frac{r}{2} - 1 - 4\alpha)[g(Y, Z)\xi - \eta(Z)Y] - (\frac{r}{2} + 3\alpha^2)[g(Y, Z) - \eta(Z)\eta(Y)]\xi, \quad (5.4)$$

using (3.1) and (3.4) in (5.4), we get

$$S(Y, Z)\xi - S(\xi, Z)Y + (-1 - 4\alpha - 2\alpha^2)g(Y, Z)\xi + (1 + 4\alpha + 2\alpha^2)\eta(Z)Y = 0 \quad (5.5)$$

Taking inner product with ξ in (5.5), we get

$$S(Y, Z) = (1 + 4\alpha + 2\alpha^2)g(Y, Z) - (1 + 4\alpha + 4\alpha^2)\eta(Y)\eta(Z) \quad (5.6)$$

Thus M is an η -Einstein manifold with respect to the Levi-Civita connection. This leads to the following

Theorem 5.1 If M is a conharmonically flat α -para Kenmotsu manifolds with respect to the semi-symmetric metric connection. Then the manifold M is an η -Einstein.

6 Example

(A 3-dimensional α -para Kenmotsu manifold with the semi-symmetric metric connection.) We consider the 3-dimensional manifold $M = (x, y, z) \in R^3, z \neq 0$, where (x, y, z) are the standard coordinates in R^3 . The vector fields

$$e_1 = z^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x}, e_2 = z^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y}, e_3 = \frac{\partial}{\partial z}$$

are linearly independent at each point of M . Let g be the Riemannian metric defined by

$$g(e_1, e_3) = g(e_2, e_3) = g(e_1, e_2) = 0,$$

$$g(e_1, e_1) = g(e_2, e_2) = g(e_3, e_3) = 1.$$

Let η be the 1-form defined by $\eta(Z) = g(Z, e_3)$ for any $Z \in \chi(M)$. Let ϕ be the (1,1) tensor field defined by $\phi(e_1) = -e_2, \phi(e_2) = e_1, \phi(e_3) = 0$.

Then using linearity of ϕ and g we have

$$\eta(e_3) = 1, \phi^2(Z) = -Z + \eta(Z)e_3$$

$$g(\phi Z, \phi W) = g(Z, W) - \eta(Z)\eta(W)$$

for any $Z, W \in \chi(M)$. Now, by direct computations we obtain

$$[e_1, e_2] = 0, \quad [e_2, e_3] = -\frac{2}{z}e_2, \quad [e_1, e_3] = -\frac{2}{z}e_1$$

by using these above equations we get[18]

$$\nabla_{e_i} e_i = \frac{2}{z}e_3 \text{ and } \nabla_{e_i} e_3 = -\frac{2}{z}e_1 \quad (6.1)$$

$$\nabla_{e_2} e_1 = \nabla_{e_1} e_2 = \nabla_{e_3} e_1 = \nabla_{e_3} e_2 = \nabla_{e_3} e_3 = 0 \quad (6.2)$$

Now we consider at this example for semi-symmetric metric connection . from (3.8) , (6.1) and (6.2)

$$\bar{\nabla}_{e_i} e_i = (\frac{2}{z} - 1)e_3 \text{ and } \bar{\nabla}_{e_i} e_3 = (-\frac{2}{z} + 1)e_1 \quad (6.3)$$

$$\bar{\nabla}_{e_i} \nabla_{e_j} = \bar{\nabla}_{e_3} e_j = 0 \text{ and } \bar{\nabla}_{e_3} = 0 \quad (6.4)$$

where $i \neq j = 1, 2$. it's known that

$$\bar{R}(X, Y)Z = \bar{\nabla}_X \bar{\nabla}_Y Z - \bar{\nabla}_Y \bar{\nabla}_X Z - \bar{\nabla}_{[X, Y]} Z. \quad (6.5)$$

By using (6.3),(6.4) and (6.5) we obtain

$$\bar{R}(e_i, e_3)e_3 = (\frac{6}{z^2} + \frac{2}{z})e_i, \quad \bar{R}(e_i, e_j)e_3 = 0$$

$$\bar{R}(e_i, e_j)e_j = (\frac{4}{z} - \frac{4}{z^2} - 1)e_i, \quad \bar{R}(e_i, e_3)e_j = 0 \quad (6.6)$$

$$\bar{R}(e_3, e_i)e_i = (\frac{2}{z} - \frac{6}{z^2})e_3$$

where $i \neq j = 1, 2$. From (2.8) and (6.6)

it's verified that

$$S(e_1, e_1) = (\frac{-2}{z^2} + \frac{2}{z} - 1)$$

$$S(e_2, e_2) = (\frac{-10}{z^2} + \frac{6}{z} - 1) \quad (6.7)$$

$$S(e_3, e_3) = (\frac{-12}{z^2} + \frac{4}{z})$$

7 CONCLUSION

If in a 3-dimensional α -para Kenmotsu manifold with the semi-symmetric metric connection , the metric g is a Ricci soliton and In this study , we gave some curvature conditions for 3-dimensional α -para Kenmotsu manifolds with semi-symmetric metric connection.In 3-dimensional α -para Kenmotsu manifolds with semi-symmetric metric connection is also an η -Einstein manifold and Ricci soliton defined steady or expanding on this manifold is named with respect to values of α and λ constant.We also proved that conharmonically flat α -para Kenmotsu manifolds with semi-symmetric metric connection is an η -Einstein manifold.

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